

Supplementary material

Original Article: Field detectability, bait response and fruit-strata use of two introduced *Zaprionus* species in tropical orchards

Table S1. McPhail trap dataset used to evaluate variation in *Zaprionus indianus* and *Zaprionus tuberculatus* abundance according to city, sampling month, attractant type, sex, temperature, precipitation, humidity and trap position.

Cidade	Mes	Especie	Atrativo	Sexo	Abundancia	Temperatura	Precipitacao	Umidade	Trap_position	Trap_position_rotation
Alagoa Grande	2024-05	Z.indianus	Proteina	Macho	3	25.3	50.5	86.9	Centre	Protein=center
Alagoa Grande	2024-05	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	1	25.3	50.5	86.9	Edge	Protein=center
Alagoa Grande	2024-06	Z.indianus	Proteina	Femea	2	23.6	234.5	89.2	Edge	Protein=edge
Alagoa Grande	2024-06	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Macho	7	23.6	234.5	89.2	Centre	Protein=edge
Alagoa Grande	2024-06	Z.tuberculatus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	15	23.6	234.5	89.2	Centre	Protein=edge
Alagoa Grande	2024-06	Z.tuberculatus	SucoGoiaba	Macho	2	23.6	234.5	89.2	Centre	Protein=edge
Alagoa Grande	2024-07	Z.indianus	Proteina	Femea	2	22.6	75.7	88	Centre	Protein=center
Alagoa Grande	2024-07	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	2	22.6	75.7	88	Edge	Protein=center
Alagoa Grande	2024-08	Z.indianus	Proteina	Femea	1	23.1	9.5	82.8	Edge	Protein=edge
Alagoa Grande	2024-08	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	3	23.1	9.5	82.8	Centre	Protein=edge
Alagoa Grande	2025-01	Z.indianus	Proteina	Femea	1	26.5	102.2	81.5	Edge	Protein=edge
Alagoa Grande	2025-01	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	1	26.5	102.2	81.5	Centre	Protein=edge
Alagoa Grande	2025-02	Z.tuberculatus	Proteina	Femea	2	25.6	129.5	84.8	Centre	Protein=center
Alagoa Grande	2025-02	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	2	25.6	129.5	84.8	Edge	Protein=center
Alagoa Grande	2025-03	Z.indianus	Proteina	Femea	3	25.9	150.2	88.4	Edge	Protein=edge
Alagoa Grande	2025-03	Z.indianus	Proteina	Macho	1	25.9	150.2	88.4	Edge	Protein=edge
Alagoa Grande	2025-03	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	11	25.9	150.2	88.4	Centre	Protein=edge
Alagoa Grande	2025-03	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Macho	1	25.9	150.2	88.4	Centre	Protein=edge
Alagoa Grande	2025-03	Z.tuberculatus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	14	25.9	150.2	88.4	Centre	Protein=edge
Alagoa Grande	2025-03	Z.tuberculatus	SucoGoiaba	Macho	1	25.9	150.2	88.4	Centre	Protein=edge
Alagoa Grande	2025-04	Z.indianus	Proteina	Femea	5	26.71	46.5	85.9	Centre	Protein=center
Alagoa Grande	2025-04	Z.indianus	Proteina	Macho	2	26.71	46.5	85.9	Centre	Protein=center
Alagoa Grande	2025-04	Z.tuberculatus	Proteina	Femea	3	26.71	46.5	85.9	Centre	Protein=center
Alagoa Grande	2025-04	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	6	26.71	46.5	85.9	Edge	Protein=center
Alagoa Grande	2025-04	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Macho	2	26.71	46.5	85.9	Edge	Protein=center
Alagoa Grande	2025-04	Z.tuberculatus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	1	26.71	46.5	85.9	Edge	Protein=center
Alagoa Nova	2024-05	Z.indianus	Proteina	Femea	2	25.2	91.5	86.9	Centre	Protein=center

Cidade	Mes	Especie	Atrativo	Sexo	Abundancia	Temperatura	Precipitacao	Umidade	Trap_position	Trap_position_rotation
Alagoa Nova	2024-05	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	21	25.2	91.5	86.9	Edge	Protein=center
Alagoa Nova	2024-05	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Macho	25	25.2	91.5	86.9	Edge	Protein=center
Alagoa Nova	2024-05	Z.tuberculatus	SucoGoiaba	Macho	1	25.2	91.5	86.9	Edge	Protein=center
Alagoa Nova	2025-01	Z.indianus	Proteina	Femea	40	26.5	81.3	81.5	Edge	Protein=edge
Alagoa Nova	2025-01	Z.indianus	Proteina	Macho	7	26.5	81.3	81.5	Edge	Protein=edge
Alagoa Nova	2025-01	Z.tuberculatus	Proteina	Macho	1	26.5	81.3	81.5	Edge	Protein=edge
Alagoa Nova	2025-01	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	1	26.5	81.3	81.5	Centre	Protein=edge
Alagoa Nova	2025-02	Z.indianus	Proteina	Femea	4	25.6	77.2	84.8	Centre	Protein=center
Alagoa Nova	2025-02	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	2	25.6	77.2	84.8	Edge	Protein=center
Alagoa Nova	2025-02	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Macho	2	25.6	77.2	84.8	Edge	Protein=center
Alagoa Nova	2025-04	Z.indianus	Proteina	Femea	2	26.71	31.5	85.9	Centre	Protein=center
Alagoa Nova	2025-04	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	12	26.71	31.5	85.9	Edge	Protein=center
Alagoa Nova	2025-04	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Macho	2	26.71	31.5	85.9	Edge	Protein=center
Alagoa Nova	2025-04	Z.tuberculatus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	4	26.71	31.5	85.9	Edge	Protein=center
Alagoa Nova	2025-04	Z.tuberculatus	SucoGoiaba	Macho	4	26.71	31.5	85.9	Edge	Protein=center
Areia	2024-05	Z.indianus	Proteina	Femea	6	22.7	93	86.9	Centre	Protein=center
Areia	2024-05	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	30	22.7	93	86.9	Edge	Protein=center
Areia	2024-05	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Macho	62	22.7	93	86.9	Edge	Protein=center
Areia	2024-07	Z.indianus	Proteina	Femea	6	20.1	170.1	88	Centre	Protein=center
Areia	2024-07	Z.indianus	Proteina	Macho	3	20.1	170.1	88	Centre	Protein=center
Areia	2024-07	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	1	20.1	170.1	88	Edge	Protein=center
Areia	2024-09	Z.indianus	Proteina	Femea	2	20.7	36.5	77.5	Centre	Protein=center
Areia	2024-09	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Macho	1	20.7	36.5	77.5	Edge	Protein=center
Areia	2025-01	Z.indianus	Proteina	Femea	4	23.9	94.6	81.5	Edge	Protein=edge
Areia	2025-01	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	3	23.9	94.6	81.5	Centre	Protein=edge
Areia	2025-01	Z.tuberculatus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	1	23.9	94.6	81.5	Centre	Protein=edge
Areia	2025-01	Z.tuberculatus	SucoGoiaba	Macho	3	23.9	94.6	81.5	Centre	Protein=edge
Areia	2025-03	Z.indianus	Proteina	Femea	7	22.6	250.3	88.4	Edge	Protein=edge
Areia	2025-03	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	2	22.6	250.3	88.4	Centre	Protein=edge
Areia	2025-03	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Macho	1	22.6	250.3	88.4	Centre	Protein=edge
Areia	2025-03	Z.tuberculatus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	1	22.6	250.3	88.4	Centre	Protein=edge
Pilões	2024-05	Z.indianus	Proteina	Femea	75	25.1	85.6	86.9	Centre	Protein=center

Cidade	Mes	Especie	Atrativo	Sexo	Abundancia	Temperatura	Precipitacao	Umidade	Trap_position	Trap_position_rotation
Pilões	2024-05	Z.indianus	Proteina	Macho	31	25.1	85.6	86.9	Centre	Protein=center
Pilões	2024-05	Z.tuberculatus	Proteina	Femea	2	25.1	85.6	86.9	Centre	Protein=center
Pilões	2024-05	Z.tuberculatus	Proteina	Macho	1	25.1	85.6	86.9	Centre	Protein=center
Pilões	2024-05	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	6	25.1	85.6	86.9	Edge	Protein=center
Pilões	2024-05	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Macho	2	25.1	85.6	86.9	Edge	Protein=center
Pilões	2024-07	Z.indianus	Proteina	Femea	2	22.6	181.8	88	Centre	Protein=center
Pilões	2024-07	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	1	22.6	181.8	88	Edge	Protein=center
Pilões	2024-07	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Macho	2	22.6	181.8	88	Edge	Protein=center
Pilões	2024-08	Z.indianus	Proteina	Femea	1	23.2	35.2	82.8	Edge	Protein=edge
Pilões	2024-08	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	21	23.2	35.2	82.8	Centre	Protein=edge
Pilões	2024-08	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Macho	6	23.2	35.2	82.8	Centre	Protein=edge
Pilões	2024-08	Z.tuberculatus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	10	23.2	35.2	82.8	Centre	Protein=edge
Pilões	2024-08	Z.tuberculatus	SucoGoiaba	Macho	3	23.2	35.2	82.8	Centre	Protein=edge
Pilões	2025-01	Z.indianus	Proteina	Femea	10	26.5	140.7	81.5	Edge	Protein=edge
Pilões	2025-01	Z.indianus	Proteina	Macho	4	26.5	140.7	81.5	Edge	Protein=edge
Pilões	2025-01	Z.tuberculatus	Proteina	Femea	16	26.5	140.7	81.5	Edge	Protein=edge
Pilões	2025-01	Z.tuberculatus	Proteina	Macho	5	26.5	140.7	81.5	Edge	Protein=edge
Pilões	2025-01	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	24	26.5	140.7	81.5	Centre	Protein=edge
Pilões	2025-01	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Macho	26	26.5	140.7	81.5	Centre	Protein=edge
Pilões	2025-01	Z.tuberculatus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	11	26.5	140.7	81.5	Centre	Protein=edge
Pilões	2025-01	Z.tuberculatus	SucoGoiaba	Macho	9	26.5	140.7	81.5	Centre	Protein=edge
Pilões	2025-02	Z.indianus	Proteina	Femea	2	25.6	50	84.8	Centre	Protein=center
Pilões	2025-02	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	5	25.6	50	84.8	Edge	Protein=center
Pilões	2025-02	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Macho	1	25.6	50	84.8	Edge	Protein=center
Pilões	2025-02	Z.tuberculatus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	4	25.6	50	84.8	Edge	Protein=center
Remígio	2024-05	Z.indianus	Proteina	Femea	2	25.2	34.6	86.9	Centre	Protein=center
Remígio	2024-05	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	46	25.2	34.6	86.9	Edge	Protein=center
Remígio	2024-05	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Macho	22	25.2	34.6	86.9	Edge	Protein=center
Remígio	2024-05	Z.tuberculatus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	26	25.2	34.6	86.9	Edge	Protein=center
Remígio	2024-05	Z.tuberculatus	SucoGoiaba	Macho	12	25.2	34.6	86.9	Edge	Protein=center
Remígio	2024-06	Z.indianus	Proteina	Femea	1	23.6	135.5	89.2	Edge	Protein=edge
Remígio	2024-06	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	10	23.6	135.5	89.2	Centre	Protein=edge

Cidade	Mes	Especie	Atrativo	Sexo	Abundancia	Temperatura	Precipitacao	Umidade	Trap_position	Trap_position_rotation
Remigio	2024-06	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Macho	15	23.6	135.5	89.2	Centre	Protein=edge
Remigio	2024-06	Z.tuberculatus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	15	23.6	135.5	89.2	Centre	Protein=edge
Remigio	2024-06	Z.tuberculatus	SucoGoiaba	Macho	14	23.6	135.5	89.2	Centre	Protein=edge
Remigio	2024-07	Z.indianus	Proteina	Femea	3	22.5	119.2	88	Centre	Protein=center
Remigio	2024-07	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	4	22.5	119.2	88	Edge	Protein=center
Remigio	2024-07	Z.tuberculatus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	16	22.5	119.2	88	Edge	Protein=center
Remigio	2024-07	Z.tuberculatus	SucoGoiaba	Macho	8	22.5	119.2	88	Edge	Protein=center
Remigio	2024-08	Z.indianus	Proteina	Femea	1	23.2	9.5	82.8	Edge	Protein=edge
Remigio	2024-08	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	2	23.2	9.5	82.8	Centre	Protein=edge
Remigio	2024-08	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Macho	1	23.2	9.5	82.8	Centre	Protein=edge
Remigio	2024-09	Z.indianus	Proteina	Femea	4	23.9	20.6	77.5	Centre	Protein=center
Remigio	2024-09	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	2	23.9	20.6	77.5	Edge	Protein=center
Remigio	2024-09	Z.tuberculatus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	1	23.9	20.6	77.5	Edge	Protein=center
Remigio	2025-01	Z.indianus	Proteina	Femea	3	26.5	53.1	81.5	Edge	Protein=edge
Remigio	2025-01	Z.indianus	Proteina	Macho	3	26.5	53.1	81.5	Edge	Protein=edge
Remigio	2025-01	Z.tuberculatus	Proteina	Femea	2	26.5	53.1	81.5	Edge	Protein=edge
Remigio	2025-01	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	7	26.5	53.1	81.5	Centre	Protein=edge
Remigio	2025-01	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Macho	6	26.5	53.1	81.5	Centre	Protein=edge
Remigio	2025-01	Z.tuberculatus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	5	26.5	53.1	81.5	Centre	Protein=edge
Remigio	2025-01	Z.tuberculatus	SucoGoiaba	Macho	4	26.5	53.1	81.5	Centre	Protein=edge
Remigio	2025-02	Z.indianus	Proteina	Femea	20	25.6	73.3	84.8	Centre	Protein=center
Remigio	2025-02	Z.indianus	Proteina	Macho	11	25.6	73.3	84.8	Centre	Protein=center
Remigio	2025-02	Z.tuberculatus	Proteina	Femea	2	25.6	73.3	84.8	Centre	Protein=center
Remigio	2025-02	Z.tuberculatus	Proteina	Macho	4	25.6	73.3	84.8	Centre	Protein=center
Remigio	2025-02	Z.tuberculatus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	7	25.6	73.3	84.8	Edge	Protein=center
Remigio	2025-03	Z.tuberculatus	Proteina	Femea	3	25.9	168.5	88.4	Edge	Protein=edge
Remigio	2025-03	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	64	25.9	168.5	88.4	Centre	Protein=edge
Remigio	2025-03	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Macho	32	25.9	168.5	88.4	Centre	Protein=edge
Remigio	2025-03	Z.tuberculatus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	69	25.9	168.5	88.4	Centre	Protein=edge
Remigio	2025-03	Z.tuberculatus	SucoGoiaba	Macho	41	25.9	168.5	88.4	Centre	Protein=edge
Remigio	2025-04	Z.tuberculatus	Proteina	Femea	6	26.71	31.6	85.9	Centre	Protein=center
Remigio	2025-04	Z.tuberculatus	Proteina	Macho	2	26.71	31.6	85.9	Centre	Protein=center

Cidade	Mes	Especie	Atrativo	Sexo	Abundancia	Temperatura	Precipitacao	Umidade	Trap_position	Trap_position_rotation
Remigio	2025-04	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	8	26.71	31.6	85.9	Edge	Protein=center
Remigio	2025-04	Z.indianus	SucoGoiaba	Macho	6	26.71	31.6	85.9	Edge	Protein=center
Remigio	2025-04	Z.tuberculatus	SucoGoiaba	Femea	14	26.71	31.6	85.9	Edge	Protein=center
Remigio	2025-04	Z.tuberculatus	SucoGoiaba	Macho	9	26.71	31.6	85.9	Edge	Protein=center

Table S2. Fruit-strata dataset used to evaluate variation in *Zaprionus indianus* and *Zaprionus tuberculatus* abundance according to city, fruit stratum, sex and species.

Cidade	Especie	Estrato	Sexo	Abundancia
Alagoa Grande	Z.indianus	Planta	Femea	7
Alagoa Grande	Z.indianus	Planta	Macho	4
Alagoa Grande	Z.indianus	Solo	Femea	16
Alagoa Grande	Z.indianus	Solo	Macho	10
Alagoa Grande	Z.tuberculatus	Planta	Femea	6
Alagoa Grande	Z.tuberculatus	Planta	Macho	4
Alagoa Grande	Z.tuberculatus	Solo	Femea	5
Alagoa Grande	Z.tuberculatus	Solo	Macho	6
Alagoa Nova	Z.indianus	Planta	Femea	0
Alagoa Nova	Z.indianus	Planta	Macho	0
Alagoa Nova	Z.indianus	Solo	Femea	1
Alagoa Nova	Z.indianus	Solo	Macho	1
Alagoa Nova	Z.tuberculatus	Planta	Femea	0
Alagoa Nova	Z.tuberculatus	Planta	Macho	0
Alagoa Nova	Z.tuberculatus	Solo	Femea	0
Alagoa Nova	Z.tuberculatus	Solo	Macho	0
Areia	Z.indianus	Planta	Femea	13
Areia	Z.indianus	Planta	Macho	6
Areia	Z.indianus	Solo	Femea	19
Areia	Z.indianus	Solo	Macho	7
Areia	Z.tuberculatus	Planta	Femea	1
Areia	Z.tuberculatus	Planta	Macho	0
Areia	Z.tuberculatus	Solo	Femea	0
Areia	Z.tuberculatus	Solo	Macho	0
Pilões	Z.indianus	Planta	Femea	0
Pilões	Z.indianus	Planta	Macho	0
Pilões	Z.indianus	Solo	Femea	15
Pilões	Z.indianus	Solo	Macho	5

Cidade	Especie	Estrato	Sexo	Abundancia
Pilões	Z.tuberculatus	Planta	Femea	0
Pilões	Z.tuberculatus	Planta	Macho	0
Pilões	Z.tuberculatus	Solo	Femea	0
Pilões	Z.tuberculatus	Solo	Macho	0
Remígio	Z.indianus	Planta	Femea	113
Remígio	Z.indianus	Planta	Macho	40
Remígio	Z.indianus	Solo	Femea	56
Remígio	Z.indianus	Solo	Macho	28
Remígio	Z.tuberculatus	Planta	Femea	73
Remígio	Z.tuberculatus	Planta	Macho	37
Remígio	Z.tuberculatus	Solo	Femea	5
Remígio	Z.tuberculatus	Solo	Macho	2

Table S3. Sampling-method dataset used to compare *Zaprionus indianus* and *Zaprionus tuberculatus* abundance between McPhail traps and fruit sampling, considering city, species, sampling method and sex.

Cidade	Especie	Metodo	Sexo	Abundancia	Method
Areia	Z.indianus	Armadilha	Male	67	Trap
Areia	Z.indianus	Armadilha	Female	41	Trap
Areia	Z.indianus	Fruto	Male	13	Fruit
Areia	Z.indianus	Fruto	Female	32	Fruit
Alagoa Nova	Z.indianus	Armadilha	Male	36	Trap
Alagoa Nova	Z.indianus	Armadilha	Female	75	Trap
Alagoa Nova	Z.indianus	Fruto	Male	1	Fruit
Alagoa Nova	Z.indianus	Fruto	Female	1	Fruit
Alagoa Grande	Z.indianus	Armadilha	Male	16	Trap
Alagoa Grande	Z.indianus	Armadilha	Female	29	Trap
Alagoa Grande	Z.indianus	Fruto	Male	14	Fruit
Alagoa Grande	Z.indianus	Fruto	Female	23	Fruit
Remígio	Z.indianus	Armadilha	Male	96	Trap
Remígio	Z.indianus	Armadilha	Female	168	Trap
Remígio	Z.indianus	Fruto	Male	68	Fruit
Remígio	Z.indianus	Fruto	Female	169	Fruit
Pilões	Z.indianus	Armadilha	Male	72	Trap
Pilões	Z.indianus	Armadilha	Female	142	Trap
Pilões	Z.indianus	Fruto	Male	5	Fruit
Pilões	Z.indianus	Fruto	Female	15	Fruit
Areia	Z.tuberculatus	Armadilha	Male	3	Trap
Areia	Z.tuberculatus	Armadilha	Female	2	Trap
Areia	Z.tuberculatus	Fruto	Male	1	Fruit
Areia	Z.tuberculatus	Fruto	Female	2	Fruit
Alagoa Nova	Z.tuberculatus	Armadilha	Male	6	Trap
Alagoa Nova	Z.tuberculatus	Armadilha	Female	4	Trap
Alagoa Nova	Z.tuberculatus	Fruto	Male	0	Fruit

Cidade	Especie	Metodo	Sexo	Abundancia	Method
Alagoa Nova	Z.tuberculatus	Fruto	Female	0	Fruit
Alagoa Grande	Z.tuberculatus	Armadilha	Male	3	Trap
Alagoa Grande	Z.tuberculatus	Armadilha	Female	35	Trap
Alagoa Grande	Z.tuberculatus	Fruto	Male	10	Fruit
Alagoa Grande	Z.tuberculatus	Fruto	Female	11	Fruit
Remígio	Z.tuberculatus	Armadilha	Male	94	Trap
Remígio	Z.tuberculatus	Armadilha	Female	166	Trap
Remígio	Z.tuberculatus	Fruto	Male	39	Fruit
Remígio	Z.tuberculatus	Fruto	Female	78	Fruit
Pilões	Z.tuberculatus	Armadilha	Male	18	Trap
Pilões	Z.tuberculatus	Armadilha	Female	43	Trap
Pilões	Z.tuberculatus	Fruto	Male	0	Fruit
Pilões	Z.tuberculatus	Fruto	Female	0	Fruit

Table S4. Summary of negative-binomial generalized linear mixed models fitted to evaluate variation in *Zaprionus* abundance. The table reports the ecological analysis, sample size, Akaike information criterion (AIC), Bayesian information criterion (BIC), log-likelihood, marginal R^2 (R^2_m), conditional R^2 (R^2_c) and the main statistical inference for each model. Marginal R^2 represents the variance explained by fixed effects only, whereas conditional R^2 represents the variance explained by both fixed and random effects. The sampling-method model controlling for sex is highlighted as the preferred sampling-method formulation because it had the lowest AIC and accounted for sex-related differences in abundance.

Analysis	N	AIC	BIC	logLik	R^2_m	R^2_c	Key inference
Bait-response model	127	813.95	845.23	-395.97	0.086	0.508	No significant global species, sex, or three-way bait x sex x species effect; pairwise test: <i>Z. tuberculatus</i> females higher in guava juice than protein ($\beta = -0.881$, $p = 0.0486$).
Fruit-strata model	40	222.84	232.97	-105.42	0.213	0.878	Significant stratum x species interaction (LRT = 6.878, $p = 0.0087$); <i>Z. indianus</i> exceeded <i>Z. tuberculatus</i> only in soil ($\beta = 2.743$, $p < 0.0001$).
Sampling-method model	40	348.02	358.15	-168.01	0.391	0.773	Trap captures exceeded fruit sampling for both species; method x species interaction not significant (LRT = 0.141, $p = 0.7077$).
Sampling-method model controlling for sex	40	345.50	357.32	-165.75	0.424	0.797	Best sampling-method model by AIC; trap > fruit for both species after controlling for sex; male abundance lower ($\beta = -0.602$, $p = 0.0266$).
Environmental model	127	807.37	827.28	-396.69	0.191	0.469	Temperature showed a positive marginal effect ($\beta = 0.194$, $p = 0.0504$; LRT $p = 0.0578$); precipitation and humidity were not significant.
Environmental model with species interactions	127	808.89	840.18	-393.45	0.244	0.531	No species-specific environmental interactions were detected (all interaction $p \geq 0.254$); used as complementary evidence.

Data availability

The datasets generated and analysed during the current study are available in the Zenodo repository: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20630208>.